

SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF EUCALYPTUS

TECHNICAL REPORT

Pakistan Forest Institute, Peshawar

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Eucalyptus is a fast-growing multipurpose tree species which has been extensively planted in about 80 countries across the globe. Due to its fast growth and good performance in harsh and unfavorable environmental conditions, the species has been planted in all provinces and territories of Pakistan. It is the best choice for plantation on barren land, river beds, saline and water-logged areas and agroforestry systems. It has been estimated that *Eucalyptus* comprises about 35% of the total tree stock on farmlands in Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Eucalyptus* is a multi-cut species which grows from coppicing and thus not only saves the high cost of re-planting but also suits the high demands for fuelwood and industrial wood of the growing Population of the country. Its wood is highly demanded by chipboard and medium-density fiberboard (MDF) industries, pulp & paper, the mining industry, construction of roofs and woodfuel. Its wood can also be used for making furniture.

Eucalyptus is a blessing for energy-deficient countries like Pakistan which highly depend on fuelwood and biomass energy. It has virtually saved the precious coniferous forests of Pakistan which were extensively used for fuelwood in the past. Now the fuelwood demands of the growing population of the country are largely met from farmlands and wastelands due to the fast growth of *Eucalyptus*. Due to its fast growth, short rotation and high market prices, *Eucalyptus* cultivation has become a significant source of income for thousands of growers in rural areas of the country. It is a main species used as fuelwood in tobacco barns, brick kilns, restaurants and households as well as a raw material for chipboard and MDF industry in the country.

Eucalyptus is also surrounded by several controversies in Pakistan. Some environmentalists blame it for depleting ground water table, some oppose it for being exotic and having negative impacts on local biodiversity while others point out its allelopathic effects on agricultural crops. Most of these allegations are based on hearsay and myths having no scientific evidence, particularly the widespread propaganda about the negative impact of *Eucalyptus* on the groundwater table is not based on any reliable research data. Pakistan Forest Institute (PFI) being the oldest and prime institute of forestry research in the country has time and again refuted such claims with scientific evidence.

Eucalyptus is an efficient utilizer of water. It produces more biomass per unit of water consumed than many other tree species like pines, shisham kikar etc. In other words, it consumes less liters of water for producing one cubic foot of wood. *Eucalyptus* consumed 0.48 liters of water to produce one gram of wood in contrast to conifers (1 liter), shisham (0.77 liter), kikar (0.72 liter), siris (0.55 liter) and jaman (0.5 liter). Conifers used more than twice the amount of water compared to *Eucalyptus* for the same quantity of wood produced.

It was proved that *Eucalyptus* roots spread more horizontally than vertically and thus consume surface and subsurface water rather than depleting the groundwater table (PFI, 2017). *Eucalyptus* exhibits an isohydric behavior that results in stomatal closure under water deficit conditions. *Eucalyptus* leaves have a thick layer of cuticles and sunken stomata which reduce water transpiration from the leaves during droughts (Ezzine et al., 2023). It is a tree species with a very conservative utilization of soil water, which adjusts to drought via stomatal control of water loss. Leaf tissue water relations, xylem anatomy, stem hydraulics and stomatal behavior are the key aspects of the water conservation strategy exhibited by *Eucalyptus* (Bourne et al., 2017).

It can be concluded that the propaganda against *Eucalyptus* cultivation is based on misperceptions. *Eucalyptus* should not be banned or excluded from plantations on the pretext of being exotic. *Eucalyptus* has become naturalized in Pakistan as it has been successfully growing in the Subcontinent for more than 400 years. It should be preferred for plantations in areas where native species are unable to produce sufficient economic and environmental benefits. Saline, water-logged and marshy places are particularly suitable for *Eucalyptus* plantations. Dry barren areas where monsoon rains are sufficient are also suitable for its plantation. However, *Eucalyptus* should not be planted in areas of High Conservation Value where it may cause detrimental impacts on local flora, fauna or ecosystem.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Eucalyptus Tree

Eucalyptus is a large, fast-growing evergreen tree widely planted in all provinces and territories of Pakistan. It is frost-hardy and grows well on a variety of soils including saline, water-logged and sodic sites. Though it is adapted to a precipitation zone of 200 to 1250 mm per year, it prefers a semi-arid warm subtropical zone which receives monsoon precipitation with a temperature range of -5 to 40°C at elevation upto 1400 m (Sheikh, 1993). It also survives in arid areas with very low rainfall but its growth is limited in such areas. It is not grazeable by animals and free from insects and pests.

The *Eucalyptus* tree belongs to the Myrtaceae family, a genus of flowering trees and shrubs. In all, there are approximately 700 different species of *Eucalyptus*, the majority of which are native to Australia. A few species are also found in New Guinea and Indonesia. It is a tall, evergreen tree that is easily adapted to dry climates and varied soil conditions. *Eucalyptus regnani* is the tallest tree in this species. It stands at an average height of 120 meters.

In addition to being tolerant of severe moisture stress and low soil fertility, these plants are also unattractive to animals and therefore widely preferred for plantation. It is composed of hard and heavy wood with a light grey sap and reddish-brown heartwood. As it is frost-hardy and light-demander, it exhibits a great variety of morphological features. *Eucalyptus* roots extend laterally beneath the soil surface to collect water and nutrients. At depths greater than 12 meters, the taproot remains short and weak and does not penetrate too deeply.

1.2 An Overview of Eucalyptus Plantation in the World

Eucalyptus is a native species of Australia. It was planted outside Australia when the British began colonizing Australia in 1788. Approximately 30 species of *Eucalyptus* were grown in England by 1830. It was in 1869 that seeds of blue gum (*Eucalyptus globules*) were planted at the Tree Fontaine near Rome. The botanic gardens of France and Italy were secondary centers of *Eucalyptus* propagation throughout the world. In North Africa and Ethiopia, the French introduced the *Eucalyptus* tree. *Eucalyptus* was introduced to China in 1890. *Eucalyptus* was introduced to the world by travellers, traders, gold miners, soldiers, priests, and botanists during the second half of the 19th century. Since *Eucalyptus* grows rapidly and is adaptable to a wide variety of environments, that is why commercial/industrial plantations have grown it for saw logs, veneer logs, pulpwood, mining, as well as non-industrial plantations – developed for fuelwood, charcoal, and domestic use. In the 20th century, *Eucalyptus* became the most successful exotic species for plantation in many parts of the world. As of today, *Eucalyptus* is planted in more than 80 countries on four million hectares in areas outside its natural range.

1.3 Introduction of Eucalyptus in the Subcontinent

In the subcontinent, *Eucalyptus* was first planted as an ornamental plant by Tipu Sultan in his palace garden on Nandi Hills in 1790. The seeds are believed to have been imported from Australia. There are about sixteen species of *Eucalyptus* that Tipu Sultan cultivated in the period of 1782-1802, which he was given by his friends in France (Handa, et al. 2002). In 1984, one *Eucalyptus tereticornis* tree from Nandi Hills was found to be 194 years old. It was 60 metres in height and 4.6 meters in diameter. Since 1856, *Eucalyptus* trees have been planted regularly in India. It was in 1860 that various species of trees were planted in northern India for the purpose of testing their viability. These trees were planted at Lucknow, Saharanpur, Dehra Dun, Agra in Uttar Pradesh, and Madhopur in Punjab. According to Chaturvedi 1976, Captain Dunn and Captain Cotton introduced *E. globulus* into the Nilgiris of the Madras Presidency(now Tamil Nadu). It is estimated that about 170 *Eucalyptus* species have been attempted up to 2200 meters altitude in the subcontinent, where annual precipitation ranges from 400 to 4000 millimetres. Agroforestry and social forestry programs during the 1970s and early 1980s accorded great importance to these species.

In 1955, PFI researchers initiated the *Eucalyptus* plantation in Pakistan. The arboretums were established in the plains at Pirowala, Changa Manga, Mianwali, and Chichawatni, as well as in the hilly regions at Ghora Gali. Small-scale trials were conducted in Fort Munro, Pirowala, Changa Manga, Gujrat, Pakhowal, Jauharabad, and Rakh Pirsabz. According to Pryor (1967), future plantations would need to be limited to five species of *Eucalyptus*, including the following: *Eucalyptus tereticornis*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *E. microtheca*, *E. melanophloia*, and *E. citriodora*. At present, *Eucalyptus* is planted in both public and private lands in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Punjab.

Figure 1 An Ariel view of Eucalyptus Plantation at Peshawar

TREE WATER REQUIREMENTS

2.1 The Water Cycle

Eucalyptus plantations have generally been criticized for their environmental effects, particularly their potential to deplete water supplies. The mechanism of water circulation between the atmosphere, the forests (or trees) and the soil must first be understood before diving deep into tree water requirements. As shown in Figure 1, there is a complex relationship between plants, soil, and water. This relationship also has an impact on local hydrology.

The main source of water is rainfall. The role of trees in rainwater distribution plays an important role in the area's tree growth and hydrology. When rain falls on an area covered with trees, some part reaches the soil directly or by dripping through the foliage, while the tree canopy intercepts some of the rain. The major part of the intercepted amount is evaporated into the atmosphere from the foliage. At the same time, a minor quantity falls on the ground either through stem flow or dripping from the foliar part. The proportional distribution of rainwater depends on many factors, including, the density of the trees, structure and texture of foliage, trunk and bark, and type of tree canopy. Besides these factors, climatic conditions like intensity and duration of rainfall, temperature, wind, etc are also important. Temperature and wind play an important role in intercepted rain water's evaporation, while the mist increases interception and subsequently to stem flow.

Figure 2 Function of tree in rain water distribution and utilization

When rainwater reaches the soil, it can take three paths: (i) flows over the surface as surface runoff, (ii) evaporates directly into the atmosphere, and (iii) infiltrate into the soil. The behavior of this water on the soil surface, including the amount of surface runoff and infiltration, depends on various factors. These include the intensity of rainfall, with heavy rainfall resulting in the greater runoff, the slope of the soil, the presence or absence of a protective layer such as leaf litter or gravel that slows water movement down the slope, and the structure and texture of the soil (Soares et al. 2001).

2.2 Role of Trees in Water Cycle

The prevailing climate and the type of vegetation present influence the movement of water within the soil. During dry seasons, the potential evapotranspiration exceeds the amount of precipitation, resulting in a net upward movement of water. Conversely, in wet seasons, the movement of soil water is different. Additionally, the movement of groundwater is dependent on the structure and texture of the soil. Water tends to move upward more easily in soils with fine textures due to capillary action than in gravel or sandy soils. When an adequate amount of water infiltrates the soil, it has the ability to hold a specific quantity of water against the pull of gravity. This phenomenon is known as "field capacity." Any excess water beyond the field capacity moves downwards towards the water table, which represents the point at which the soil becomes consistently saturated. From there, this water can flow in different directions, including towards streams, rivers, or deep underground aquifers.

Plants that establish their roots within the field capacity zone of soil have the ability to utilize a significant portion of the accessible water. They absorb a portion of this water into their living tissues and release the remaining amount into the atmosphere through evapo-transpiration. The specific quantity of water utilized depends on factors such as climate, root distribution, and the extent of soil occupied by the roots. The presence of trees plays a crucial role in regulating water both above and below the soil surface. However, the effectiveness of water regulation varies depending on the species of trees. *Acacia* species and tropical broad-leaved trees like teak are particularly effective at intercepting rainfall, with *Acacia* species having the highest interception rates.

On the other hand, scrub tree species show the lowest interception rates. Conifer tree species intercept more than 37% of rainfall water, surpassing the interception rates of *Eucalyptus* species. This suggests that conifers experience greater evaporation loss of rainfall water. *Eucalyptus* species and scrub species demonstrate similar levels of rainfall interception. Broad-leaved tree species exhibit the highest stem flow of rainfall, followed by *Eucalyptus* species. The stem flow in *Eucalyptus* species is approximately 1.6 times greater than that of conifers. Stem flow water is crucial for tree growth as it falls within the tree's root zone, making it readily available for absorption. Additionally, this water rinses off chemicals present on the stem surface and contributes to the soil. Among the different species, *Eucalyptus* species exhibit the highest throughfall of rainfall, while *Acacia* species have the lowest throughfall. The significant amount of stem flow and throughfall in *Eucalyptus* species indicates a greater proportion of rainfall reaching the soil surface (Honeysett et al. 1996).

Figure 3 Potential of different tree species to intercept rainfall.

2.3 Hydrological Response of Different Species

The hydrological impact of trees in a catchment and the performance of the trees are significantly affected by whether they have access to continuous underground water or if they rely solely on moisture replenished by local rainfall. When tree roots can access groundwater, they do not experience water shortages. However, in arid climates, trees will consume water based on their specific needs, which are generally influenced by temperature and wind conditions. Conversely, when trees depend on rainfall and the replenishment of soil moisture through rainfall, the amount of water available to them is influenced by the climate, particularly the seasonal variations in the ratio between precipitation and potential evapo-transpiration.

A study conducted by PFI at the Pabbi Forest area in Kharian, Punjab aimed to assess the impact of various land use practices on sediment yield. Fifteen plots, each measuring 300 square meters and having a slope of five percent, were designated for this purpose. The study included five different treatments: agriculture crops without soil conservation measures, agriculture crops on terraced land, tree cover consisting of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Leucaena leucocephala*, perennial grasses, and cultivated fallow. The agriculture plots were planted with Mung crops, and runoff resulting from four rain storms during the monsoon season was analyzed.

The findings revealed that the highest recorded runoff was 115 mm in the Agriculture plot, followed by 109 mm in the grasses plot. Conversely, the plot planted with *E. Camaldulensis* and *L. leucocephala* exhibited the lowest runoff at 62 mm. Similarly, the *E. Camaldulensis* and *L. leucocephala* plot showed the lowest hydrological response of 21.1% and the lowest sediment yield of 1.3 ton/ha/year. On the other hand, the agriculture plot had the highest hydrological response of 39.2% and the highest sediment yield of 5.7 ton/ha/year (Table 3). These outcomes highlight the stabilizing and sustainable effects of tree plantation, particularly with *E. camaldulensis*, in the catchment area.

Figure 4 Effect of different treatments on the hydrological characteristics of catchments

Mathur et al. (1976) conducted a study in north India near Dehra, involving two watersheds measuring 0.87 and 1.87 hectares, respectively. One watershed was covered with natural scrub, while the other was planted with a mixture of *E. grandis* and *E. camaldulensis*. Both catchments were observed and calibrated over an 8-year period. The forested catchment had a slope of 5.1%, whereas

the other catchment had a slope of 9.5%. Results showed that the afforested catchment experienced a 28% reduction in runoff and a 73% reduction in peak rate. Furthermore, the Eucalyptus plantation was accompanied by dense scrub regrowth. Approximately one-fifth (1/5th) of the plot's surface was cultivated at the time of planting, which could contribute to the observed outcomes. In a related context, de la Lama (1982) highlights the significance of terracing in *Eucalyptus* plantations to mitigate surface runoff and enhance infiltration. Lima and O'loughlin (1984) reviewed the water quality in catchments containing natural Eucalyptus forests and concluded that the quality is generally good. Furthermore, they found that water quality primarily depends on geological and soil properties rather than the vegetation type.

2.4 Tree Water Requirement

The Pakistan Forest Institute conducted a study at the Changa Manga irrigated plantation to evaluate the water requirements of different forest tree species. Four tree species, namely *Populus deltoids*, *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, and *Paulownia tomentosa*, were subjected to six irrigation treatments replicated four times. Trenches were prepared at 3.0-meter intervals in each plot, with planting slots at 2.0-meter spacing. In February 1992, 80 plants of each species were randomly planted. To minimize experimental errors caused by lateral movement of soil moisture, the 80 tree-plots were surrounded by four rows of plants. *E. camaldulensis* and poplar were planted as whole plants, while the remaining species were planted as stumps. To supply measured amounts of irrigation water, four-meter flumes were constructed, and the following intervals were used:

- T1: Irrigation once a week
- T2: Irrigation once every two weeks
- T3: Irrigation once every three weeks
- T4: Irrigation once every four weeks
- T5: Irrigation once every five weeks
- T6: Irrigation once every six weeks

The overall findings indicated a significant impact of irrigation intervals on the four tree species. The growth of trees was only marginally different when irrigated weekly or every two weeks. However, increasing the irrigation interval beyond two weeks negatively affected tree growth. The effect of irrigation intervals varied among the different tree species. The highest growth reduction, at 23.5%, was observed in *P. deltoids* when the irrigation interval was extended from 7 days to 45 days, followed by a 22.9% reduction in *P. tomentosa*. The lowest growth reduction was found in *D. sissoo* (4.71%), followed by *E. camaldulensis* (7.2%), when the irrigation interval was extended from 7 days to 45 days (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Mean diameter (cm) of three years old plants

2.5 Water Consumption by Tree Species

Comprehensive empirical data on water usage and water balance in plantations are crucial for assessing their environmental impact and developing optimal land use strategies. Recent research conducted in various countries, such as Australia, Brazil, Portugal, South Africa, India, and Pakistan, has enhanced our understanding of the hydrology of *Eucalyptus* and other non-native tree plantations.

In a study conducted by Afzal et al. (2018), the water consumption of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Tamarix aphylla* was compared in Noorpur Thal. The results revealed that *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* exhibited a higher water use efficiency (WUE) of 1.3783 g/L, whereas *Tamarix aphylla* had a lower WUE of 0.9858 g/L, showing a significant increase of 23.92%. Furthermore, plant height was found to be greater for *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* (251 cm) than *Tamarix aphylla* (232.17 cm) regardless of soil media. There was a 27.43% increase in the dry biomass of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* compared to *Tamarix aphylla* (670.40 g) in *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*. A plantation of *Eucalyptus* on marginal lands can adapt to drought conditions and can produce even more biomass than the slow-growing native species resistant to droughts.

Similarly, Mahmood et al. (2001) conducted a study to monitor tree growth, water usage, and climate and soil conditions between 1994 and 1998 in young plantations of *Eucalyptus*, *Acacia*, and *Prosopis* at two locations: Lahore and Faisalabad. As described by Edwards and Warwick (1984) and modified by Olbrich (1991), the heat pulse method was employed to measure tree water usage. At Lahore, on a plantation level, *E. camaldulensis* and *E. microtheca* exhibited daily water consumption of 3.82 ± 0.07 mm and 2.87 ± 0.06 mm, respectively. Regarding underground saline water, *E. camaldulensis* consumed 3.20 ± 0.07 mm and 2.99 ± 0.09 mm of water daily in low and high salinity conditions, respectively (Figure 6). *E. camaldulensis* utilized more than 0.95 mm (33%) additional water daily compared to *E. microtheca* in Lahore. The study also revealed the significant impact of salinity on water consumption by *E. camaldulensis*. In underground low-saline water conditions of Faisalabad, *E. camaldulensis* consumed over 0.21 mm (7%) more water daily compared to underground high saline water. Furthermore, the findings indicated variations in daily mean water usage based on the location. *E. camaldulensis* demonstrated higher daily mean water usage at Lahore compared to Faisalabad. On an individual tree basis, the maximum water usage rates observed were 70 liters and 77 liters per day for *E. camaldulensis* and *E. microtheca*, respectively, at Lahore, and 56 liters per day for *E. camaldulensis* at Faisalabad.

Figure 6 Mean daily water use by *Eucalyptus* at Lahore & Faisalabad

Eucalyptus camaldulensis, grown on an irrigated site near Lahore that was not affected by salinity, exhibited optimal growth until the age of 5 years. It had an annual water consumption of 1393 mm. Similarly, *Eucalyptus microtheca* in Lahore, which was also irrigated, and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in Faisalabad, relying on saline groundwater without irrigation, utilized over 1000 mm of water per year. Mahmood et al. (2001) observed a close relationship between water usage by tree species and their basal area growth and sapwood area. The water consumption of tree species varied significantly with the changing seasons. *Atriplex ampliceps* and *Prosopis juliflora* had mean annual water usages of 624 mm and 235 mm, respectively. The lower sap flux density (SFD) of *A. ampliceps* and *P. juliflora*, compared to *E. camaldulensis* in Faisalabad, suggests that these species respond differently to site conditions, which restricts their water usage independently from their growth responses. Besides SFD, the *P. juliflora* stand had sparse tree distribution and incomplete canopy cover. The water table depth at Faisalabad (site PL), where the groundwater was low in salinity, was usually more than 3.3 m below the surface, occasionally becoming as shallow as 2.5 m during monsoon rains and dropping below 3.5 m between October and December. Comparisons with piezometer data from other locations in Faisalabad (Pacca Anna) indicate that the water table depth at the three other plots was approximately 1.2 m shallower than at the PL site. Fluctuations of up to 35 cm in the water table depth were observed daily beneath the *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* stand at the PL site, which did not result from groundwater pumping but likely represented direct uptake of groundwater by the tree roots when soil moisture in the unsaturated profile was depleted (Mahmood et al., 2001).

A study conducted by Hafeez and Basharat (2002) on a mature *eucalyptus* plantation near the Pindi Bhattian area was chosen to investigate water table levels, root zone salinity, and evapotranspiration under mature eucalyptus trees.

In comparison with the surrounding cropped area, water table depth decreased by 0.30 to 0.40 meters beneath the eucalyptus plantation. Nevertheless, after cutting down 25 acres of the plantation, the previously lowered water table level rapidly increased due to the lack of transpiration. Based on the analysis of the data, it was determined that eucalyptus plantations had no effect on groundwater quality. Moreover, the plantation and rainfall contributed to the reclaiming of the land, thereby eliminating the visible salinity patches that existed before the plantation. *Eucalyptus* plants evapotranspire approximately 70 liters per day. A drainage coefficient of 1mm/day is required to maintain a desired level of water table depth of approximately 4,047 liters per acre per day.

Figure 7 Mean annual water use by *Eucalyptus* at Lahore & Faisalabad

It is possible to accomplish this with 58 eucalyptus trees, thus providing an alternative to engineering solutions. *Eucalyptus* plantations are an environmentally friendly and cost-effective method of producing biomass. This study concluded that plantations with a high evapotranspiration rate, such as eucalyptus, are capable of improving waterlogged and saline lands located in permanently humid regions. Prior to implementing this approach, careful consideration should be given to waterlogged lands in semi-humid regions that experience cyclical changes in dry and wet periods. (Hafeez and Basharat, 2002).

Water use by *Eucalyptus* varies globally, depending on the species and location. The amount of water utilized by *Eucalyptus* ranged from 542 mm per year in China (Morris et al., 2004) to 2300 mm per year in Western Australia (Sweeney and Frah, 1992). It was discovered that by establishing plantations at wider spacing, water usage by *Eucalyptus* could be reduced in areas with high water availability and high vapour pressure deficit (VPD). These findings align with Hafeez and Basharat's research (2002). The water usage by *Eucalyptus* observed in Pakistan generally aligns with the global findings. Overall, the water consumption by Eucalyptus is comparable to other tree species such as *Acaica nilotica*, *Baccharis sp.*, *Poplars*, *Prosopis sp.*, *P. pallid*, and *Tamarix* species. *A. ampliceps* and *P. Julifora* utilize less water compared to other tree species. However, Mahmood et al. (1998) attributed this lower water usage to the sparse population of these particular tree species.

Figure 8 Water consumption by Eucalyptus at different localities

Nazli, et al. (2020) assessed the impact of Eucalyptus plantations on groundwater availability in six parks in Lahore. They reported that there were 3484 Eucalyptus trees of different age classes in these parks planted in 1990. The groundwater level has significantly reduced in these areas which they attributed to Eucalyptus trees without considering other factors that might have affected the groundwater level e.g. increase in groundwater pumping by tube wells, a decrease in groundwater recharge due to a reduction of water flow in Ravi river and the impacts of climate change. Furthermore, they applied rates of water loss by Eucalyptus in other countries without comparing the soil and climatic conditions of those countries to the target areas. Thus the study has major limitations and cannot be taken as reliable scientific evidence to ascertain the impact of Eucalyptus on ground level.

2.6 Water Consumption and Biomass Production

Plants, including trees, require nutrients from the soil and water to grow. They absorb mineral nutrients dissolved in water through their roots and transport them to all living parts, such as branches, leaves, flowers, and fruits. During this process, water is used to carry the nutrients and some of it evaporates through the leaves, a process called transpiration. The remaining nutrients are retained in the trees. Young trees need approximately 300 to 500 units of water to produce one unit of woody matter. Previous research compared the water consumption of different tree species and found that *Eucalyptus* consumed 0.48 liters of water to produce one gram of wood. In contrast, other species like Kikar, Siris, Shisham, Jaman, and kanji required varying amounts of water per gram of wood. Conifers used more than twice the amount of water compared to *Eucalyptus* for the same biomass. *Eucalyptus* has shown high growth and productivity, which is why it was introduced to the Indian Subcontinent. The average annual growth of *Eucalyptus* per hectare was approximately eight (08) cubic meters, with the potential to reach up to 40 cubic meters, whereas indigenous trees averaged 0.50 cubic meters. This higher productivity leads to an increased demand for water. Additionally, a study found that *E. tereticornis* was the most efficient in biomass production per liter of water consumed out of ten (10) species tested.

Figure 9 Water consumption and biomass production of different tree species

Likewise, a study compared the water use efficiency of *Eucalyptus* with various agricultural crops. The findings indicated that, except for Sorghum (shown in Figure 12), agricultural crops utilized significantly more water per unit of biomass production than *Eucalyptus* (Davidson, 1992).

Figure 10 Water consumption and biomass production of different plant species

2.7 An Investigation to the Root System of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*

In order to study the root system of *Eucalyptus*, PFI conducted a research study in 2017, wherein a mature *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* tree was selected in Research Garden. The tree had an age of 18 years, diameter of 15 inches and height of approximately 81 feet. Soon after digging approximately half feet from the base of the tree at ground level, lateral roots become visible. At about 3 to 4 feet of further digging, these roots straightened and started moving horizontally inside the ground. The largest lateral root was measured and found to be 56 feet long, followed by another one of 47 feet, then 30 feet and another of 28 feet, respectively. No proper taproot was found. However, the taproot length was measured and found to be 12 feet, whereas the lateral roots and depth of the vertical root were measured and found to be 16 feet long. This investigation revealed that the roots of *Eucalyptus* spread horizontally and not vertically deeper to reach the groundwater table. The lateral development of roots indicates that *Eucalyptus* depend on surface water.

Figure 11 Root of *Eucalyptus* dug out at PFI, Peshawar showing lateral spread

2.8 Physiological Response of *Eucalyptus* to Water Deficits in Arid Climate

Some tree species have been gifted by nature a diverse set of morphological anatomical and physiological responses that provided them with the ability to cope with water stress conditions. *Eucalyptus* is one of such species which has developed several water conservation strategies to survive and grow under water stress and droughts in arid and semi-arid climates (Ezzine et al. 2023).

Eucalyptus exhibits an isohydric behavior that results in stomatal closures under water deficit conditions. It has a thick layer of cuticle and sunken stomata which reduce water transpiration from the leaves during droughts. Besides, leaf tissue water relation, xylem anatomical stem hydraulics and stomatal behaviors are the key aspects of water conservation strategy exhibited by *Eucalyptus* (Bourne et al. 2017).

EFFECT OF EUCALYPTUS PLANTATION ON SOIL QUALITY

3.1 Effect of Eucalyptus Plantation on Soil Erosion

Plantations of *Eucalyptus*, similar to other types of vegetation, can have a positive impact on soil erosion by providing ground cover that protects land against erosive forces. Chinnamani et al. (1965), in their study conducted in the Nilgiris, India, observed minimal soil loss under scrub, broom grassland, and *Eucalyptus* plantations. However, they did note some slight erosion immediately after site preparation and thinning. Harcharik and Kunkle (1978) concluded that most *Eucalyptus* trees are not effective for erosion control. When young, they are highly susceptible to competition from grass and require thorough weeding during the establishment period, which is not ideal on steep or eroding terrain. Even mature stands may not effectively prevent surface runoff.

Stein (1952) observed that in steep, arid areas where *Eucalyptus globulus* had been planted, the understory vegetation and litter accumulation were insufficient to prevent surface runoff, indicating a weak effect on soil erosion. Closed plantations of *Eucalyptus* have high water demands and an extensive, dense root system that allows them to successfully compete for available soil moisture, particularly against smaller, shallow-rooted plants. This often leads to poor development of understory vegetation, leaving the soil exposed to runoff. In such cases, Stein recommended thinning dense stands, wider spacing during planting, or irrigation to promote understory growth. Therefore, dense *Eucalyptus* plantations are generally not recommended for erosion control, especially in semi-arid climates, unless their litter production can compensate for a sparse understory or if combined with engineering measures or cover crops.

Figure 12 *Eucalyptus* plantation at DI Khan

Moreover, (Jensen, 1983) also revealed that *Eucalyptus* is also commonly planted as shelter belts on farmlands, providing some protection against wind erosion. However, this protection is solely a physical phenomenon, and its effectiveness depends solely on the physical characteristics of the site and the shelter belt itself. The specific species of *Eucalyptus* used does not significantly influence the outcome. Thus, *Eucalyptus* has a similar effect to other tree species when used as a shelter belt.

3.2 Effect of Eucalyptus Plantation on Nutrients Availability

Observations have demonstrated that different tree species have an impact on certain characteristics of the soil. Over the long term, trees bring about notable changes in soil properties, contingent upon the specific species and soil type in a given environment. Trees play a role as nutrient pumps by recycling leached nutrients from deeper soil layers to the topsoil. Additionally, the decomposition of organic matter from tree litter is expected to enhance the soil's biological, physical, and chemical properties (Forrester, et al. 2006).

A comparative study examining the effects of *Eucalyptus* spp. and native *Acacia* spp. revealed that in the 0-10 cm soil layer, the proportions of sand and silt under *Eucalyptus* plantations were similar to those of the corresponding layer in the control plots with native *Acacia*. However, the clay content in plantation soil was significantly higher at a 1% confidence level. In the immediate subsoil layer of 10-20 cm, there were no significant differences in the sand proportions between *Acacia* and *Eucalyptus* spp. The bulk density and total porosity of the 0-10 cm layer in plantation soil were similar to those of the *Acacia* control plots.

For both the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm soil layers, there were no significant differences between plantation and native species in terms of exchangeable potassium levels. However, exchangeable calcium and magnesium were significantly lower in plantation soil, despite its higher clay content. This disparity was particularly evident in the 0-10 cm layer, where the cation exchange capacity in plantation soil was reduced to 83% of that in the native soil. The availability of phosphorus was low in the soil under both *Eucalyptus* plantation and native *Acacia* in 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm soil layers (Guedes 2016). This indicates that both tree species have limited ability to mobilize phosphorus from inorganic sources in the subsoil. Soil pH was significantly lower in the soil under *Eucalyptus* in both the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm layers due to the immobilization of exchangeable bases, especially calcium. This decline in pH would lead to a decrease in soil base saturation. The electrical conductivity (ECe) of the saturation extract of the plantation soil ranged from 1 to 4 dSm⁻¹ and increased significantly with depth, likely due to salt leaching.

Soil nutrient depletion is not exclusive to *Eucalyptus*. It is a common issue in monoculture plantations, particularly with fast-growing tree species that immobilize soil nutrients faster than they recycle. Different tree species selectively immobilize soil nutrients, resulting in varying effects on soil nutrient levels. Other species have also been observed to deplete exchangeable calcium, magnesium, and potassium in the topsoil. Pine plantations, for instance, have shown a decline in soil calcium, magnesium, and phosphorus levels (Forrester, et al. 2006).

Soil nutrient deficiency can limit plantation productivity after multiple rotations. It is crucial to rehabilitate the soil by applying appropriate fertilizers and potentially lime to increase soil pH and base saturation at the end of each rotation before replanting. Additionally, since tree harvesting at

the end of each rotation leads to significant nutrient loss from the ecosystem, it is important to adopt soil-conserving harvesting techniques. Discouraging whole tree harvesting, which depletes soil nutrients, and allowing the decomposition of nutrient-rich twigs and leaves in the plantation can help reduce nutrient drain. *Eucalyptus* exhibits allelopathic effects, which refer to the positive or negative direct or indirect influence of one plant on another through releasing chemical compounds into the environment. These chemical compounds, known as allelochemicals, are released from various parts of the plant through processes such as leaching.

Figure 13 Phenomenon of Trees Allelopathy

An experiment was carried out to evaluate the effects of soil allelopathy, allelochemical volatilization, and foliage litter decomposition on the germination and growth of *Albizia lebbek*, an introduced species, in a plantation consisting of *Eucalyptus* and Pine. The growth of *Albizia lebbek* was not significantly different between the two plantations. The study concluded that the allelopathy observed in the *Eucalyptus* plantation only inhibited the growth of native tree species and had no significant impact on *Albizia lebbek*. Based on the findings, it was recommended that *Albizia lebbek*, a nitrogen-fixing species, could be considered for the establishment of mixed stands with *Eucalyptus* (Chu, et al. 2014).

3.3 Role of Eucalyptus in Soil Enrichment

One critique of *Eucalyptus* trees is that they have the potential to deplete nutrients in the soil, especially when they are grown and harvested repeatedly over multiple cycles. This criticism applies to fast-growing tree species in general, including *Eucalyptus*. It is important to determine the validity of this claim and whether there is any specific evidence indicating that *Eucalyptus* trees have higher requirements than other species.

On the contrary, there are assertions that planting *Eucalyptus* trees on degraded or deforested sites can actually enhance soil characteristics. This improvement can be attributed to the trees' ability to enhance the structure of the topsoil, penetrate relatively impermeable subsoil layers, and draw nutrients from deeper soil layers.

Figure 14 *Eucalyptus* plantation at DI Khan

George (1979) reported the nutrient contents in the rainfall, stem flow, and throughfall within a *Eucalyptus* plantation. The concentrations of nutrients can be found in Figure 16. The highest quantity of potassium, ranging 9.4 kg/ha/year, was introduced to the soil through the throughfall of rainwater. Similar outcomes were observed for calcium and nitrogen. In general, it was discovered that throughfall exhibited higher salt concentrations compared to stem flow, while both channels had greater salt concentrations than rainwater. Attiwill (1966) conducted further research and concluded that the primary source of nutrients was the leaching of nutrients from *Eucalyptus* leaves. Stem flow may be crucial in delivering nutrients directly to the feeding root zone. These findings highlight the vital role of *Eucalyptus* in the nutrient cycle, while conclusive evidence regarding the effect of *Eucalyptus* on inputs remains limited.

Similarly, Mengistu, et al. (2022) also reported that the land uses of *Eucalyptus* plantations and croplands are not significantly different from one another. While the soil organic carbon and soil organic matter values of *Eucalyptus* plantation land were higher than those of cropland. This is due to the fact that organic matter is recycled through the decomposition of different parts of the trees. Crop land is subject to significant depletion of soil nutrients as a result of intensive agricultural systems that focus on cereal crops. *Eucalyptus* spp, however, appears to be capable of improving the physical and chemical properties of soil through the decomposition of litter, in contrast to croplands, which are intensively cultivated.

Figure 15 Nutrients return by *Eucalyptus* through precipitation

GROWTH AND BIOMASS PRODUCTION OF EUCALYPTUS

Eucalyptus is a fast-growing tree species which produces more biomass and wood compared to other tree species. the Productivity of *Eucalyptus* is significantly higher in areas where sufficient moisture is available due to irrigation or high rainfall.

Data collected from Buner showed *Eucalyptus* plantations raised in hilly areas are producing large quantities of wood. These plantations are harvested after every five years. After harvesting the plants re-sprout from coppicing. In some areas these plantations have been harvested for four-five times and each time the new plantation has produced more wood than the previous one. Secondly, there is no cost for re-planting due to coppicing. Wood production of 250 mounds per acre was reported after 05 years old plantations which have been harvested four times in the past. In this area, local landowners were able to earn Rs. 100,000/- from a one-acre hilly area after 05 years of *Eucalyptus*. This is a tobacco-growing area where natural coniferous forests have been severely deforested in the past for fuelwood for tobacco curing. However, now *Eucalyptus* plantations have saved these valuable forests.

On the other hand in dry areas like Dera Ismail Khan (D.I.Khan) an average production of 350 mounds per acre was recorded from the *Eucalyptus* plantation raised under BTAP Project. The *Eucalyptus* wood is highly demanded by the MDF industry and can fetch a price of Rs. 500-600 per mound. In this area, farmers are getting up to Rs. 175,000/- per acre from *Eucalyptus* plantations after 05 years.

Eucalyptus is the major tree species in Punjab, South and Central zone of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, comprising 35.17% of the total growing stock, whereas Zizyphus, Phulai, Poplar, Kikar and Shisham contribute by 9.27%, 8.63%, 8.17%, 7.06% and 6.86% respectively. Other important tree species having significant contributions are Tamarix (4.40%), Bakain (4.15%), Olive (3.6%), Siris (1.41%) and Mulberry (1.07%). *Eucalyptus* and poplar are the two main species planted in the area. However, kikar and bakain are also planted in some areas.

4.1 Biomass Production and Growth Performance of Eucalyptus under Irrigated Conditions

Eucalyptus camaldulensis was studied in irrigated plantations by PFI to determine how much fresh biomass is produced. The average biomass production per hectare was found to be 18 tons per year. Depending on the age of the plantation, biomass production varied significantly. There was a substantial increase in biomass production in the first 10 years, which was 20.5 tons per hectare per year. In recent years, biomass production has averaged 14.3 tons per hectare per year. Consequently, about ten years is the optimal rotation for *Eucalyptus* plantations. The biomass productivity of *Eucalyptus* will decline after ten years if it is retained. The figure below illustrates this phenomenon.

Figure 16 Eucalyptus biomass production and growth performance under irrigated conditions

Figure 17 A view of mature Eucalyptus plantation

A comparative study was conducted at Peshawar to evaluate the fresh biomass production of *Eucalyptus* in comparison to other species. The results in the table below revealed that Poplar exhibited the highest biomass production (34.67 t/ha/year), while *Eucalyptus* followed closely with a production of 24.67 t/ha/year. Additionally, after a span of 3 years, *Eucalyptus* plants demonstrated significant growth, with an average diameter at breast height (DBH) of 9.4 cm and a height of 12.2 m. These findings indicate that *Eucalyptus* exhibits exceptional growth rates, comparable to poplar, particularly when provided with irrigation.

Figure 18 Fresh biomass production of Eucalyptus vs. other species at Peshawar

4.2 Biomass Production and Growth Performance of Eucalyptus under Rainfed Conditions

Information was gathered from plantations established as part of the Billion Trees Afforestation Project (BTAP) in the dry regions of Dera Ismail Khan (D.I. Khan). The study revealed that *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* exhibited the highest biomass production in arid areas of D.I. Khan, specifically 6.82 tons per hectare per year after four years of plantation. Conversely, *Acacia nilotica* plantations yielded a fresh biomass of 12.10 tons per hectare per year. In the case of mixed plantations, the fresh biomass reached 13.30 tons per hectare per year. In a study conducted by Zahid et al. (2010), the growth performance of *Acacia*, *Albizzia*, *Azadirachta*, and *Eucalyptus* was compared in the arid environmental conditions of Multan. After one year of planting, the survival rate of *Acacia*, *Albizzia*, *Azadirachta*, and *Eucalyptus* were 84%, 82%, 81%, and 100%, respectively. The average air-dried total biomass per plant produced from one-year-old *Acacia*, *Albizzia*, *Azadirachta*, and *Eucalyptus* was 56 g, 95 kg, 24 g, and 203 g. Similarly, the average dry shoot biomass per plant was 36.55 g, 42.07 g, 6.79 g, and 102 g, and the average root biomass per plant (dry) was 19.52 g, 52.93 g, 19.26 g, and 100 g, respectively. The average height of one-year-old *Acacia*, *Albizzia*, *Azadirachta*, and *Eucalyptus* were 115 cm, 107 cm, 55 cm, and 200 cm, respectively. The average girth of the plant at the root collar was 34 mm, 54 mm, 19 mm, and 62 mm, respectively. In another study by Shairazi et al. (2006), the height of 9-month-old *Acacia* and *Eucalyptus* was reported to be about 200 cm and 190 cm, respectively. Furthermore, the reported height of *Eucalyptus* and *Azadirachta* grown in a container under salt-stress conditions was 43.1-168.4 cm and 13.5-52.5 cm, respectively, according to Suriyan and Kirdmanee (2008).

The ability of a tree species to produce biomass affects its capacity to provide fuel, fodder, and other benefits. In cases where wood production is a key objective for landowners, fast-growing tree species should consume less water per unit of wood produced. *Eucalyptus* trees produced 2-8 times more biomass than native species while consuming 2-3 times less water. This performance translated into better Transpiration Coefficient (TC) and Water Use Efficiency (WUE) for *Eucalyptus* than for native species. According to Zahid et al. (2010), *Eucalyptus* was a highly efficient water user with a TC of 739 L/kg, which was much lower than the TC of *Acacia*, *Albizzia*, and *Azadirachta*, which required 1042 L, 872 L, and 1951 L of water to produce one kg of biomass.

4.3 *Eucalyptus* Growth on Saline and Waterlogged Soil

Eucalyptus has shown a high level of survival in harsh environmental conditions, according to a study conducted by PFI (2018) in D.I.Khan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Eucalyptus* survived 94% of the time in wet conditions and 85% of the time in salty conditions four years after being planted. The dry biomass produced by *Eucalyptus*, when grown in wet conditions, is greater than that of the *Acacia nilotica* (kiker). On the other hand, the annual dry biomass yield in saline regions was measured at 2.40 tonnes per hectare.

Figure 19 Survival percentage of tree species under waterlogged and saline conditions

Rawat & Banerjee (1998) observed in the potted experiment by using different salinity levels (40, 80, 120, and 160 mM) to seedlings of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and shisham (*Dalbergia sissoo*) in pot culture, and evaluated the effects of the salt on the development, dry-matter production, and photosynthesis of leaves. Plants survived salinities as high as 160 mM with varying degrees of growth and dry matter production. The stems of plants, notably *E. camaldulensis*, gained dry weight in response to salinity, but the leaves and other parts of plants lost dry weight. The total dry-matter production of both *E. camaldulensis* and *D. sissoo* were promoted by salinization at all salinity concentrations except 40 mM. Protein and chlorophyll content and the rate of photosynthesis in the leaves were not comparable between the two species. The plant's protein and chlorophyll concentrations dropped across the board, but at 40 mM, the plant's photosynthetic carbon absorption was stimulated. The rate of leaf photosynthetic activity and the amount of dry matter produced were not found to be related in any clear way. The results showed that both species responded well to low salt concentrations in terms of growth, biomass production, and photosynthetic rate, while *E. camaldulensis* seemed more salt-resistant than *D. sissoo*.

In the Hula Valley, Israel, Zohar (1989) conducted a study on the cultivation and yield of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* over a four-year cycle, focusing on both neutral and acidic peat soils. Throughout most of the year, the water table at the site ranged from 1 meter to 2 meters. The trees were planted at varying densities of 1100, 1670, and 3300 trees per hectare. The favorable combination of fertile soil, high water table, and elevated temperature provided optimal growth conditions, resulting in remarkably high biomass and energy production levels. The type of peat and stocking density above 1670 stems per hectare did not have any impact on biomass production. For stocking densities of 1670 stems per hectare, the average annual increment of above-ground biomass was 51 metric tons (dry) per hectare per year, while the average annual energy production reached 1008 MJ/ha per year. Upadhyaya and Soni (1997) studied the growth characteristics, distribution of organic matter, and contribution of different parts to the total biomass of a five-year-old plantation of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in Rajasthan, India. The plantation had a spacing of 2 m × 2 m. The height of the trees ranged from 5 m to 20 m, and the girth at breast height varied between 15 cm and 69 cm. On average, the plantation had a girth of 13.55 m and a height of 12.01 m. Trees with larger girths had a higher proportion of bole-wood and usable biomass, while non-utilizable biomass was less prominent. The total biomass yield of the plantation was 185.12 oven-dry tonnes per hectare, with a usable biomass of 147.19 oven-dry tonnes per hectare.

Bernardo et al. (1998) conducted a study in the savannah region of central Minas Gerais state in southeastern Brazil to assess the growth and biomass accumulation of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *E. Urophylla*, and *E. Pellita*. The trees were planted at three different spacings: 3x1.5 m, 3x3 m, and 4x3 m. After 41 months, the average height of *E. camaldulensis* was 10.4 m, while *E. pellita* and *E. urophylla* had heights of 8.4 m and 12.1 m, respectively. The average diameter of *E. camaldulensis* at that age was 8.2 cm, compared to 9.0 cm for *E. pellita* and 10.5 cm for *E. urophylla*. Spacing had minimal impact on height growth, but wider spacing led to increased individual diameter growth due to reduced competition. The biomass produced by *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* after 41 months was 53.3 t/ha, 50.8 t/ha, and 48.7 t/ha for the respective spacings mentioned above.

Farahat (2012) conducted a study in Egypt to estimate the growth dynamics and total above-ground biomass (TAGB) of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in plantations of different ages (8 years, 11 years, and 13 years) under irrigated conditions. The study included three plantation sites: El-Tur

forest, Wadi El-Natrun, and Sarapium. The stem densities in these sites were 750 stems/ha, 900 stems/ha, and 1005 stems/ha, respectively. The mean tree heights recorded at these sites were 10.7 m, 9.7 m, and 13.5 m, and the corresponding diameter at breast height (DBH) were 22.3 cm, 15.1 cm, and 14 cm. Despite being the youngest plantation (8 years old), *E. camaldulensis* in Sarapium forest had the highest TAGB of 173.2 t/ha. In comparison, the TAGB in El-Tur (13 years old, flood irrigation) and Wadi El-Natrun (11 years old, drip irrigation) was approximately 62% and 53% of that obtained in Sarapium, respectively.

4.4 *Eucalyptus* Growth in other Countries

Upadhyaya and Soni (1997) concluded that the growth characteristics, distribution of organic matter, and contribution of different parts to the total biomass of a five-year-old plantation of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* in Rajasthan, India. The plantation had a spacing of 2 m × 2 m. The height of the trees ranged from 5 m to 20 m, and the girth at breast height varied between 15 cm and 69 cm. On average, the plantation had a girth of 13.55 m and a height of 12.01 m. Trees with larger girths had a higher proportion of bole-wood and usable biomass, while non-utilizable biomass was less prominent. The total biomass yield of the plantation was 185.12 oven-dry tonnes per hectare, with a usable biomass of 147.19 oven-dry tonnes per hectare.

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CARBON SEQUESTRATION POTENTIAL OF EUCALYPTUS

Climate change is exacerbated by forest plantations due to their role as important carbon sinks. It is through the growth of trees that carbon is sequestered and stored in their biomass and soil. There are many factors that influence the rate of carbon sequestration, including tree species, age, climate, and site conditions. Carbon sequestration potential varies among tree species. Fast-growing tree species have a high capacity to sequester carbon, and when raised on a long rotation, they can remove a significant amount of carbon from the atmosphere.

Due to its rapid growth and high biomass production, *Eucalyptus* is considered to have a high carbon sequestration potential. The forest ecosystem stores carbon in five different pools: above-ground biomass, belowground biomass, dead wood, litter, and soil organic matter. Besides storing a considerable amount of carbon in above-ground and belowground biomass, *Eucalyptus* plantations also contribute to the enrichment of soil carbon by increasing the litter layer on the ground floor. Furthermore, they contribute to the accumulation of coarse woody debris and understory vegetation that act as secondary carbon sinks. There are certain *Eucalyptus* species that have a long life, such as *Eucalyptus citridora* and *Eucalyptus regnans*, which can act as carbon reservoirs for a long time. According to Keith et al. (2009), *Eucalyptus regnans* forest in Victoria, South Eastern Australia has the highest biomass carbon stock in the world (1867 t/ha). The IPCC (2006) reported that *Eucalyptus* Plantations can sequester 20-40 tonnes of carbon dioxide per hectare per year, which is one of the highest levels of carbon sequestration by plantations.

As shown in the following figure, different tree species sequester carbon under irrigated conditions at 3 years of age at Peshawar. A comparison has been made between *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and poplar in terms of their ability to sequester carbon. It is estimated that poplar trees can sequester CO₂ up to 30 t/ha per year, while *Eucalyptus* trees can sequester up to 26 t/ha per year. The carbon sequestration rate for *Acacia nilotica* (Kiker) and *Leucaena leucocephala* (Ipilipil) in this area was 24 t/ha/year and 15 t/ha/year, respectively.

In contrast, the carbon sequestration rate of *Eucalyptus* and other species in dry areas of Dera Ismail Khan has been determined to be approximately 7 tons of carbon per hectare per year. Irrigated areas sequester almost one third of their carbon. The reason for this is that irrigated soils produce trees that grow faster and accumulate a greater amount of biomass. According to findings, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* sequesters CO₂ at a rate of 7.40 tons per hectare per year at the age of four, which is slightly higher than *Acacia nilotica*, which sequesters 6.5 tons per hectare per year. Carbon sequestration in mixed plantations was 7.21 tons per hectare per year.

Figure 20 Carbon sequestration by different tree species

The Billion Trees Afforestation Project (BTAP) has successfully planted a significant quantity of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* trees in the saline, water-logged, and dry wastelands of central and southern parts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The project has recorded a total area of 227,502 hectares planted under BTAP, with 126 million of these being *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* trees. These trees are estimated to sequester approximately 861,525 metric tons of carbon dioxide per year. Additionally, 30.4 million *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* trees have been planted on farmlands, contributing to a carbon sequestration potential of 190,219 metric tons of CO₂ per year. Therefore, the overall carbon sequestration potential of the *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* trees cultivated through the BTAP Project amounts to 1,051,744 metric tons of CO₂ per year.

However, there are specific requirements that must be met to access result-based payments under the REDD+ Programme. These requirements, known as Social and Environmental Safeguards of REDD+, ensure that actions are aligned with the conservation of natural forests and biological diversity. In addition, the use of monoculture exotic species is discouraged as carbon credits with biodiversity value command higher prices. Another crucial requirement for REDD+ is the permanence of actions, which necessitates maintaining forest cover for a significant period, typically no less than 2-3 decades. Conversely, *Eucalyptus* plantations are typically managed on shorter rotations, usually less than 10 years.

It is possible to manage *Eucalyptus* plantations for REDD+ benefits if certain policy-level decisions are implemented. These decisions include establishing plantations on state land, preferably in waterlogged and saline areas where they can be maintained for an extended period to support REDD+. Furthermore, sustainable management practices are necessary to ensure that a minimum forest cover is preserved over a prolonged duration, thereby meeting the requirements for REDD+. Additionally, *Eucalyptus* plantations can serve as an alternative source of wood, allowing for the management of natural forests for carbon sequestration and other ecosystem services.

In the Pearl River Delta (PRD) in Southern China, fast-growing *Eucalyptus* and *Acacia* species are favored for plantation purposes. A study conducted in 21 plantations of varying ages between 1989 and 2003 examined the pattern of biomass accumulation and carbon sequestration. The study found that biomass accumulation increased with stand age, reaching 207.45 t/ha in mature *Eucalyptus* plantations and 189.35 t/ha in *Acacia* plantations. The contribution of secondary biomass from the understory, litter layer, and Coarse Woody Debris accounted for 10.2% and 20.3% of the total biomass in the respective plantation types. The *Eucalyptus* and *Acacia* plantations in the PRD accumulated a substantial amount of biomass and sequestered carbon. Most of the plantations (82.1% for *Eucalyptus* and 89.3% for *Acacia*) were in the young to middle-aged stage. *Acacia* plantations exhibited a higher biomass density compared to *Eucalyptus* plantations. Forest management intensification and reforestation programs, particularly targeting *Acacia* or mixed *Eucalyptus/Acacia* forests, show promising potential for future carbon sequestration.

Zhou et al. (2017) investigated changes in plant biomass carbon (C) and soil organic carbon (SOC) storage across a chronosequence of *Eucalyptus urophylla* x *Eucalyptus grandis* forests in subtropical China. The study examined forests of different ages (4, 7, 10, 13, and 21 years). The results showed a significant increase in biomass carbon stock with stand age. SOC storage initially increased after afforestation, peaking in 10-year-old stands, but gradually declined afterward. Ecosystem carbon pools across the five development stages were 111.76, 167.66, 234.04, 281.00, and 299.29 Mg ha⁻¹, respectively. Trees and soils were the primary carbon pools across all stand ages, with tree biomass carbon storage increasing significantly while SOC storage decreased with age. *Eucalyptus* plantations in subtropical China are still experiencing vigorous growth and possess substantial potential for carbon sequestration by the end of the current rotation length (within 7 years). However, considering the sharp decline in annual biomass carbon increment rate and the gradual loss of SOC storage in stands older than 13 years.

PROPERTIES OF EUCALYPTUS WOOD

Eucalyptus has excellent strength properties and is a highly dense wood. Due to its moderate hardness, cleavage, and tensile strength values, this wood is more suitable for machining, routing, nailing, and boring. As the wood has a relatively low modulus of rupture, modulus of elasticity, and compression properties, it may not be suitable for high load-bearing structures, such as beams.

The harvesting of *Eucalyptus* trees should be carried out between December and January in order to obtain timber. Once the logs have been harvested, they must be immediately sawn into planks. To reduce the development of defects during the production process, the planks should be cut into 2 to 3 inches in thickness at the beginning. To ensure a smooth and regular flow of air through the planks, the planks should be stacked correctly under the shed. Using the proper seasoning technique, wood will become seasoned within about two months and be ready to be further processed in accordance with the product's requirements. *Eucalyptus* wood has a Runkel ratio of less than 1 and is suitable for use in pulp and paper manufacturing. It has a reasonable degree of flexibility and felting power ratio, as well as a low degree of rigidity co-efficient ratio. In terms of flexibility, folding endurance, binding and mating strength, and bursting strength, the paper produced from *Eucalyptus* wood has quite a bit more flexibility than that produced from other woods; however, the paper may have only a moderate tearing resistance.

Following are tables of *Eucalyptus* wood's physico-mechanical properties and pulp properties of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, respectively.

Table 1: Strength properties of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*

S #	Property	Units	Average value
1	Modulus of rupture	(kg/cm ²)	788
2	Modulus of elasticity	(kg/cm ²)	74168
3	Maximum compression parallel to grain	(kg/cm ²)	356
4	Maximum compression perpendicular to grain	(kg/cm ²)	111
5	Cleavage	(kg/cm)	27
6	Tensile strength perpendicular to grain	(kg/cm ²)	26
7	Impact bending	(m-kg /4 cm ²)	0.2
8	Hardness Side End	(kg)	583 636
9	Density	(Kg/m ³)	705
10	Calorific Value	(Kcal/Kg)	4900

Table 2: Pulp Properties of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*

S#	Property	Value
1.	Runkel ratio (2 x fiber cell wall thickness/ lumen width)	0.68
2.	Flexibility ratio (fiber lumen width/ fiber diameter)	0.59
3.	Felting power ratio (fiber length/ fiber diameter)	54.14
4.	Rigidity co-efficient (fiber wall thickness/ fiber diameter)	0.20

USES OF EUCALYPTUS

Figure 21 Different kinds of furniture made of Eucalyptus wood

7.1 Eucalyptus Wood and its Uses

Eucalyptus wood has a density of 705 kilograms per square meter. In addition to having good machining properties, routing properties, nailing properties, and boring properties. Modulus of rupture, modulus of elasticity, and compression properties do not allow it to be used in construction. Particleboard can be manufactured using these mechanical properties. Furthermore, it can be mixed with low density woods for manufacturing the particleboards of desired density. It is also possible to manufacture veneers and plywood from *Eucalyptus* wood. Compared with other hardwoods commonly used to make pulp and paper, *Eucalyptus*' fibers are relatively short, uniform, slender and thick walled, with a low coarseness. In addition to good pulp yield, relatively good fiber properties enable the production of opaque papers with smooth surfaces, high grammage with good density, better flexibility, and folding endurance, medium binding and mating, good bursting strength, good tearing resistance, and good printing. It is also important to note that the low coarseness of the fiber, as well as the high number of fibres per gram of fiber, are important for the production of high-quality coated papers and tissue papers.

Eucalyptus wood possesses a high calorific value. During the drying process, it burns efficiently and produces a minimal amount of ash. A high carbonization rate makes it an ideal material for producing charcoal. *Eucalyptus* wood charcoal provides approximately 7,900 calories per kilogram, whereas raw wood yields approximately 4,700 calories per kilogram. Nevertheless, the production of charcoal requires 1.25 to 3 times more wood than it consumes to generate the same amount of energy, which results in significant energy loss in the process. Eucalyptus is a fuelwood species with a calorific value comparable to Shisham (*Dalbergia sissoo*) and Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*).

Regarding density, *Dalbergia sissoo* measures 801 kg per m³, and *Acacia nilotica* measures 833 kg per m³. The wood density of these two species is slightly higher than that of Eucalyptus; however, the latter exhibits a faster growth rate. The yield of air-dried wood from *Eucalyptus* plantations per hectare annually can be up to 10.86 tons, which is greater than the yields from *Dalbergia sissoo* and *Acacia nilotica* plantations of 5.21 tons and 10.08 tons per hectare per year, respectively. It is becoming increasingly recognized, however, that Eucalyptus trees are associated with numerous long- and short-term problems, despite their numerous advantages. There are numerous issues associated with plantations, including soil degradation, reduced water availability, and negative impacts on wildlife.

Despite its high density and strength, *Eucalyptus* is a very hard wood. After careful processing, the wood can be used for furniture, poles, rafters, door frames, and frames for windows. However, the wood may prove to be somewhat difficult to saw and work on. Preservative treatment may be required prior to using the wood to make various wood products, as the wood may not be very durable. Despite this, the process of seasoning and preserving the wood may take a long time. Particleboard panels can be manufactured from Eucalyptus wood that is between 4 and 8 years old. In addition, high-density wood can also be used to make particleboard by mixing it with low-density wood. The Eucalyptus tree produces a fair amount of pulp and can be used as a raw material in the production of paper. It produces papers with smooth surfaces, high grammages, good density, good flexibility, folding endurance, medium binding strength, and tear resistance, and can be used for printing purposes.

Figure 22 Particle board made of *Eucalyptus* wood

Figure 23 Use of *Eucalyptus* logs in developing glamping site at the historic Munro track, Mansehra

7.2 Case Studies

7.2.1 *Eucalyptus* use by ZRK Group of Industries:

ZRK is the top *Eucalyptus* wood consumer industry in Pakistan which produces MDF products of export quality. The daily *Eucalyptus* demand of the ZRK Industry is 15,000 tonnes, while the current daily supply is only 10,000 tonnes. Thus there is a gap of 5000 tonnes/day. The average price of *Eucalyptus* wood offered to farmers is Rs. 550/maund. The diameter of the *Eucalyptus* plant used by ZRK industries ranged from 2-15 inches in diameter. The total number of employees involved in *Eucalyptus*-related work in ZRK is about 10,000. Besides *Eucalyptus* other wood like *Sesbania sesban*, *Poplar*, *Tamarix*, Sugarcane bagasse, sawdust, match sticks without ignition powder, Ber, and Kiker are also used. Although the demand for *Eucalyptus* is growing, its supply has remained stagnant, leading to the utilization of other species to meet the demand. However, despite the availability of other options, *Eucalyptus* is still the preferred choice. ZRK industries export *Eucalyptus* products (MDF) to Afghanistan, the Middle East, and Central Asian countries.

7.2.2 *Eucalyptus* use by Frontier Greenwood Industries:

The daily *Eucalyptus* demand of Frontier green wood Industries (FGWI) is 15,000 tonnes, while the current daily supply is only 2 tonnes. The reason is that mostly the *Eucalyptus* crop grown is purchased by ZRK industries, and if the FGWI import the wood from other provinces, then they cannot match the price of ZRK because of the high cost of wood. The annual increase in demand by FGWI for *Eucalyptus* was predicted as 5000 tonnes/day. The average price of *Eucalyptus* wood is Rs. 600/mound.

The diameter of the *Eucalyptus* crop used by FGWI ranged from 6-8 inches in diameter. The total number of employees involved in the *Eucalyptus*-related work in FGWI is about 700. The use of alternative species, such as *Sesbania sesban*, *Poplar*, *Tamarix*, and Sugarcane bagasse, has been increasing due to the rising demand for *Eucalyptus*, which an equivalent increase in supply has not met. Although other species are being utilized to address the demand, *Eucalyptus* remains the preferred choice. The speaker went on to note that the demand for *Eucalyptus* is currently outstripping supply, leading the industry to explore permanent alternatives in the hope of reducing this demand in the future. FGWI export *Eucalyptus* products to Afghanistan.

At present, the industry has been temporarily shut down due to a limited supply of *Eucalyptus* and raw materials. The cost of importing these materials from Punjab is steep, making it difficult to compete with the prices offered by ZRK Group of Industries, which uses *Eucalyptus* grown in Mardan.

Figure 24 *Eucalyptus* wood supply to ZRK and FGWL industries, Peshawar

7.3 Economic Advantages to Local Communities

In a study conducted in Malakand by Khan and Manan (2016), it was determined that Rs.19,451,090/- was spent on planting 19,854 acres of Eucalyptus on 56 different sites, including the beating up of failures and the watch and ward. The Forest Department has made all expenditures through various projects and schemes without any contribution from the landowner communities. As a result of the plantation activities, there were job opportunities for the local communities, and economic activity was generated in the form of labour. From this activity, a total revenue of Rs. 242 million was earned by the local communities.

Data collected from 12 farmers in district Malakand revealed that an average income of Rs. 8.61 million was earned by each farmer from the sale of Eucalyptus wood harvested from their land after a span of five years. Similarly, in the district, Mardan 08 farmers collectively earned Rs. 193 million from the sale of Eucalyptus trees over the 450-hectare area in 2018 after 05 years of plantation. Likewise in district Swabi, a landowner earned a total revenue of 8 million from Eucalyptus plantation over 15 hectares in 2018. These plantations were raised under the BTAP project.

7.4 Eucalyptus Plantation Potential for Apiculture

Apiculture, or beekeeping, plays a vital role in agricultural ecosystems and global food production through pollination services and honey production. *Eucalyptus* plantations, known for their rapid growth and extensive foliage, offer a promising environment for apiculture. Here we provide a detailed analysis of the potential benefits, challenges, and considerations associated with establishing beekeeping operations within *Eucalyptus* plantations.

Abundant Nectar and Pollen: *Eucalyptus* trees produce large quantities of nectar and pollen, which serve as vital food sources for bees (Bisui et al., 2020). The profuse flowering of *Eucalyptus* species throughout the year ensures a continuous supply of forage for bees (Marchini & Moreti, (2003); Mora et al., 2009). Different *Eucalyptus* species vary in their nectar production levels, with some species producing larger quantities of nectar than others (Ekomono, (2020).

Figure 25 *Eucalyptus* flowers bloom

- **Honey Quality:** Bees that forage on *Eucalyptus* trees can produce honey with distinct flavors and aromas. *Eucalyptus* honey is often characterized by its strong, menthol-like taste and is highly valued by consumers. Studies have shown that the composition and sensory characteristics of *Eucalyptus* honey can vary depending on the *Eucalyptus* species and the geographic region where the bees forage (Marchini et al., 2005; Palmieri et al., 2022).
- **Bee Behavior:** Bees foraging on *Eucalyptus* flowers exhibit specific behaviors. They tend to collect nectar from the base of the flower, where the nectaries are located. The presence of abundant nectar resources in *Eucalyptus* trees can attract large numbers of bees and result in intense foraging activity (Malkamäki et al., 2016). However, some researchers have noted that *Eucalyptus* nectar can be difficult for bees to access due to its high viscosity, which may affect foraging efficiency.
- **Impact on Honeybee Colonies:** *Eucalyptus* plantations can have both positive and negative effects on honeybee colonies (Malkamäki et al., 2016). The availability of nectar from *Eucalyptus* flowers can provide a significant food source for bees, supporting colony growth and honey production. However, monocultures of *Eucalyptus* trees may lack floral diversity, limiting the availability of other important nectar and pollen sources for bees. Additionally, the use of pesticides in *Eucalyptus* plantations can pose risks to bee health.

Figure 26 Bee foraging on *Eucalyptus* flowers

- **Ecological Considerations:** It is important to consider the ecological impact of *Eucalyptus* plantations on native bee species and the overall ecosystem. Eucalyptus trees are often introduced species in many regions, and their dominance can lead to changes in plant communities and potentially displace native floral resources. This can have implications for native bee populations and other pollinators.
- Overall, research suggests that *Eucalyptus* species have the potential to support apiculture due to their abundant nectar production. However, it is crucial to promote floral diversity and consider the ecological context when establishing *Eucalyptus* plantations for honey production, ensuring the sustainability of beekeeping and the preservation of native pollinators and ecosystems.

Figure 27 Bee hive in *Eucalyptus* tree at PFI Research Garden

7.5 *Eucalyptus* as a Fuelwood Source

A survey was conducted in connection to *Eucalyptus* as fuelwood in the outskirts of Peshawar. The private owners are of the opinion that due to *Eucalyptus*'s rapid growth and high calorific value; it has a potential fuelwood source in Pakistan. It can tolerate drought and adapt to various soil conditions. Furthermore, the cost of one mound is Rs.550/-.

7.6 Other Uses

Eucalyptus is a versatile plant known for its many uses. Here is a detailed list of some of the common uses of *Eucalyptus*:

- **Essential oils:** Eucalyptus oil is extracted from the leaves of the *Eucalyptus* tree and is widely used in aromatherapy, massage oils, and as an ingredient in various cosmetic and personal care products. It has a refreshing and invigorating scent (Ghorab et al., 2009).

- Medicinal purposes: *Eucalyptus* leaves and oil have medicinal properties. They are used to relieve symptoms of respiratory conditions such as coughs, colds, sinus congestion, and bronchitis. *Eucalyptus* oil is often found in over-the-counter cough and cold medications (Ashour et al., 2008).
 - Insect repellent: The strong aroma of *Eucalyptus* acts as a natural insect repellent. It can be used to deter mosquitoes, flies, and other insects. *Eucalyptus* oil is often found in insect-repellent sprays, lotions, and candles (Gomes et al., 2013).
 - Respiratory health: The inhalation of *Eucalyptus* oil vapours can help clear nasal congestion and improve breathing. It is commonly used in steam inhalation, chest rubs, and nasal sprays (Karimpour et al., 2018).
 - Pain relief: *Eucalyptus* oil is sometimes used topically as a natural remedy for joint and muscle pain. It can be found in creams, ointments, and massage oils designed to provide relief from conditions like arthritis, sprains, and strains (Jun et al., 2013).
 - Household cleaning products: *Eucalyptus* oil is an effective natural disinfectant and is often used in household cleaning products. It helps kill bacteria, viruses, and fungi, making it useful for cleaning surfaces, floors, and even laundry (Hong-yan et al., 2009).
 - Industrial uses: *Eucalyptus* wood is highly valued for its durability and strength. It is commonly used in construction, furniture making, flooring, and crafting (Nogueira et al., 2019; Sarker et al., 2022).
 - Paper production: *Eucalyptus* trees are a significant source of fiber for paper production. Their fast growth and high yield of cellulose make them suitable for the paper and pulp industry (Camargo et al., 2014).
 - Ornamental and landscaping purposes: *Eucalyptus* trees and shrubs are popular choices for landscaping due to their attractive foliage and unique appearance. They are often used to provide shade, windbreaks, and privacy in gardens and parks.
 - Aesthetic and therapeutic value: *Eucalyptus* branches and leaves are often used in floral arrangements, wreaths, and potpourri due to their pleasant scent and attractive appearance. They are also used in saunas and steam rooms to create a soothing and relaxing ambiance.
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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Eucalyptus plantations are highly productive and rapidly growing, making them valuable for timber and commercial use. They are extensively cultivated worldwide due to their adaptability to various climates and soil conditions. Local communities benefit from *Eucalyptus* plantations through income generation and employment opportunities while promoting regional development and reducing reliance on natural forests for timber.

Eucalyptus has performed exceptionally well in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab and Sindh provinces. It is well adapted to the local climatic and soil conditions. The species has become the first choice for plantation in harsh, tough and unfavourable sites where there are low prospects for survival and growth of other tree species. Saline, water-logged and marshy places are particularly suitable for *Eucalyptus* plantations. Similarly, it is also growing well in the subtropical zone receiving more than 500 mm of rainfall per year. In extremely arid areas, though it survives but its growth is limited due to shortage of water particularly after 7-8 years. *Eucalyptus* is also a good choice for agroforestry in humid, sub-humid and semi-arid areas. It provides an additional source of income to the farmers in 5-6 years and minimizes the risks associated with crop failure due to climatic impacts.

Eucalyptus wood has many uses ranging from fuelwood to industrial wood. It is highly demanded by the chipboard, MDF, pulp and paper industries. It is also used in roof construction and the mining industry as pit props. *Eucalyptus* wood can also be used for making furniture. *Eucalyptus* plantations also support apiculture and honey production.

The controversies surrounding *Eucalyptus* are based on misperceptions. In contrast to the general misperception that *Eucalyptus* depletes the groundwater table, the species has developed a special mechanism by which it reduces water loss during drought and dry periods. *Eucalyptus* roots spread more horizontally than vertically and thus consume surface and subsurface water rather than depleting the groundwater table. *Eucalyptus* exhibits an isohydric behaviour that results in stomatal closure under water deficit conditions. *Eucalyptus* leaves have a thick layer of cuticle and sunken stomata which reduce water transpiration from the leaves during droughts. It is a tree species with a very conservative utilization of soil water, which adjusts to drought via stomatal control of water loss. Leaf tissue water relations, xylem anatomy, stem hydraulics and stomatal behaviour are the key aspects of the water conservation strategy exhibited by *Eucalyptus*.

Eucalyptus is an efficient utilizer of water. It produces more biomass per unit of water consumed than many other tree species like pines, shisham kikar etc. In other words, it consumes less liters of water for producing one cubic foot of wood. *Eucalyptus* consumed 0.48 liters of water to produce one gram of wood in contrast to conifers (1 liter), shisham (0.77 liter), kikar (0.72 liter), siris (0.55 liter) and jaman (0.5 liter). Conifers used more than twice the amount of water compared to *Eucalyptus* for the same quantity of wood produced. Its evapotranspiration losses are less than other tree species.

It is advisable to consider the following recommendations for the *Eucalyptus* plantation.

- *Eucalyptus* has become naturalized in Pakistan as it has been successfully growing in the Subcontinent for more than 400 years. Therefore, it should be treated as naturalized rather than exotic species in the country.
- It should be preferred for plantations in areas where native species are unable to produce sufficient economic and environmental benefits.
- Saline, water-logged and marshy places are particularly suitable for *Eucalyptus* plantations. Dry barren areas where monsoon rains are sufficient are also suitable for its plantation.
- *Eucalyptus* should be mixed with other native species such as Acacias and other Nitrogen fixing trees and shrubs to augment soil fertility and aesthetic value.
- *Eucalyptus* should not be planted in natural forest areas of High Conservation Value e.g. coniferous forests where it may cause detrimental impacts on local flora, fauna or ecosystem.
- *Eucalyptus* should not be planted near drainage systems, water supply pipelines or buildings.
- Its plantation on fertile agricultural land should be avoided.

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